

ISSUANCE OF ADS ON SITES

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Annotation: this article is written about marketing in online journalism, about business planning using advertising policies.

Keywords: online, advertising, marketing, internet, business:

One of the main components of editorial management and the conditions for its success is marketing. Marketing is understood as the study of the market for online publications and the determination of the place of their publication in it, the study of the opinions of the audience of readers and the activities of competitors. Special specialists marketers are engaged in Marketing activities. They are led by a marketing manager whose activities are journalism aware must be a professional who understands the demands of a market economy well. The first and most important task of a marketer is to research the audience in which he operates. They also include information such as publication users. The second important task is to study the audience of users. Another competitor from Marketing goals is to research the activities of internet publications. For this, sometimes, having studied each issue of a competitive internet publication, the topic and content of its materials design information about ads is summarized and presented to the management of editorial representatives. They use this information to develop a competitive strategy. In the Marketing process, the publication ordered the use of its trademark also plays an important role. Recommendation marketing is a continuous process. As long as the Internet is blessed, marketing becomes available financial manager regularly oversees the marketing effect of marketing work. Mobodo will take organizational and economic measures to understand the situation if it gives an unexpected result. The editorial office's advertising policy provides for certain discounts and allowances from the placement of advertising on the web page. Additional tools left when printing an ad at the discretion of the master advertiser including color form to get a special number should be given in a form that differs from other ads. For additional services will be charged discount for long-term maturity of advertising can be issued for large amounts of annual conclusion of the contract to a large amount. Prices for advertising are determined by editorial managers who specify the allowance and discounts to keep them changing. The editorial staff of advertisers will determine how the

financial policy for the New Year of Finance is planned. To do this, the expected income of the editorial office is first calculated after all expenses. If the expenses exceed the income manashu compensate for the difference it can be changed to the cost of advertising. At the same time, when the pricing policy for advertising is being carried out, the price of advertising in competitive things the situation in the advertising market is also referred to as the solvency of advertisers. After that, the area that will be allocated for placing ads from the page will be marked. According to the advertising law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in a media without an advertising publication, products of an advertising nature should not exceed 40% of the total volume of the page. The area reserved for advertising is measured in Rex profitability to achieve and generate more revenue, the cost of advertising can be hidden in such a way that both the editorial and the advertiser are equally satisfied. The editorial office is considered to be the basis for planning the entire financial activities of the editorial board of the business planning business. It is the responsibility of the financial manager of the editorial office to prepare it so that it is also long-term and the general manager and editor-in-chief participate in its discussion and approval. The financial results of the activities of the editorial office of the business plan of all expenditure income are reflected in the market requirements. A business plan is developed in an elementary manner to certain established norms, the degree of which from the type of its basis will be unchanged. It is clear that the work of editorial creative units and their employees is difficult for business planning of a person in relation to commercial departments in order to achieve this, it will be necessary to introduce business planning into the activities of economic thinking skills in journalists and form a culture of understanding that its implementation is in their interests.

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